

The Impact of Working Life and Personal Life Balance in an Organizational Environment: A Review Paper

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Abstract:- This study's aim is to review various articles from different sources which is able to understand the effect of balancing the working life and personal life of employees. The study is based on "Impact of work-life balance in an organization: a review paper", extensive research on literature review has been done with the help of sourcing various articles from different search engines. It is identified that various tables, charts, and figures are helpful to understand the full concept of work and non-work life balance. The finding of this study is to observe various factors from different sourced articles that need to be focused on for future periods. We reviewed articles from different countries their point of view has been taken successfully. The study represents a comprehensively explore and research of the impact of working life and personal life balance in an organizational environment. It explores professional life and personal life, it discusses different authors' perspectives based on that limitation, recommendations and discussion are drawn in this review paper. Therefore, this review paper has collected recent information which will help other researchers. A detailed overview about working life balance and personal life balance review paper has been completed in a proper way.

Keywords:- Working Life Balance, Personal Life Balance, Managing Both Work And Life, Organizational Environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this 21st century balancing work is very essential for everybody. In a family, work can be shared by husband and wife this way they make their life easy-going. This study is based on working life as well as personal life of employee's in a organizational environment. Balancing of work and personal life provides quality employment all over the full course that allows for leisure and family time in a long-run. It is important to improve work and life together for better societal outcomes. (Misun Lim, 2020).

In this review paper in-depth research has been done from various sources, this paper described the work-life balance of an employee. As an employee of a company, one needs to concentrate on one working life as well as personal life altogether without any difficulties, it has various benefits and consequences as per various authors from different countries may found. There are many techniques used to get

rid of many issues and implement good suggestions over it. The factors like, flexible working-life-balance, gender differences, cultural differences, psychological empowerment, job satisfaction, digitalization (technology), and conflict.

During covid-19 pandemic most women faced problems due to overwork load and handling both work, children, old parents, husbands, household work, etc, but day-by-day it has become obvious to handle situations from every perspective. Nowadays women are willing towards doing work remotely and they are experts to handle situation. This study shows both working couples in a family must manage and balance their life and work cooperatively and happily, so coordination is important between them. Many authors shared their views on what a future study should be on. It is the clear view of what is required to make work-life balance unbiased in a certain unexpected organizational environment. Thus this study focuses on different facts that affect work-life-balance, then methodology part is designed to understand the data recorded during research from sources, years of articles, and a number of countries forward to may solve this issue of work-life and then a few portals are used to gather information, it will be easy to identify these with the help of a diagram. From this study the framework helps to understand factors that are connected, focus on those factors to it is become easier to solve issues and start working on underdeveloped areas. The drawback table from many authors' ideas helps to get an overview of the problems mentioned in this review paper. As per the description of the authors, we drawn limitations in this study and made an effective conclusion and recommendation for further research.

II. OVERVIEW

A. Work and life balance

This is needed for every individual's life those who working in any sector to male or female. It balances the professional and personal life (family, career, vacations etc.). It is mostly useful and expresses free from conflict between working and non-working demands. (Greenblatt, 2002). There are various great impacts of work-life balance such as low absentees and arrive late at office, enhance productivity, better organizational image, employ honesty and commit towards work, raise job retention of employees and reduce staff turnover rates, Job-satisfaction improve etc.,. (IOAN LAZĂR, 2010) These will occur in a positive way if both men and women can balance their personal life and

professional life together. Occasionally, balancing a family and work together is unattainable this may occur due to anxiety, stress, fatigue, etc. As Dr. Heidi Gautun said ‘The full-time work of a person may reduce family member’s able to help and care to their old parents’ (Dr. Heidi Gautun, 2023).

According to (Jae Won Yang, 2018) A woman will balance work and family (children, and home) together. Kalonaityte said a women’s role in work-life balance is like an active agent, who attempts to balance contradictorily and demand for gender division of labour and work. (Kalonaityte, 2023).

B. Definations of Work-life Balance

A well Balanced employee is happy and satisfied with work and family together . (THOMAS KALLIATH, 2008)

According to (Delecta, 2011) It is not limited to some extent it demands more such as vacations, sports, and personal development programs etc. They managing time along with personal work and professional with proper balancing way. According to (N. Lakshmi, 2018) “Work-life balance experience happiness and life situation”

C. Factors of Working and personal life Balance

There are many important factors which is taken from many sources are given below:

➤ *Flexible Work-life balance*

Flexibility needs during work for everyone, which makes an individual manage work and life in an effective way. In work-life balance flexible work is enabled for employees at the workplace and for friendly working practices it required flexible time, term-time work, four days and a half-day week, work sharing, and a 9-day fortnight. (Fleetwood & Steve, 2007). Employees being in a flexible environment create interest in jobs and happily manage work and home. In Table 1 employee’s flexible work practice has been mentioned.

Table-1 Employee friendly flexible work practice (Fleetwood & Steve, 2007)

Employee’s friendly flexible work practice	
Flexible time	2647350
Term time work	1173825
Four days and a half-day work	324675
Work Sharing	224775
9-day fortnight	74925

➤ *Gender Differences*

Balancing work and life is different from person to person if we discuss men and women their professional life is almost similar but their personal life has many differences such as managing the home, caring for elders, child care, etc. A study mention gender differences focused in the relationship between the roles of work and family rather than work and non work community based role. (TracyL.Dumas, 2013). In certain situations, the problem of balancing will

solve due to the coordination of both genders working husband and wife to handle work and family together.

➤ *Cultural Differences*

In cultural differences a diverse cultural background forms in the heterogeneous work environment. This cultural difference shows through academic work, family life, expectations towards institutional support, and many more.

➤ *Psychological Empowerment*

It is a manifestation of internal motivation, and this is very important act in the balance of working life and personal life which facilitates success in an organization by adopting a cultural synergy, self-based awareness, collaboration, self-determination, and partnering, these all improve psychological empowerment level. It enhances loyal, honest, honour, and trust etc. (Ansumalini Panda, 2021)

➤ *Job Satisfaction*

Self-satisfaction is very important without it we cannot gain interest in any kind of work. Job satisfaction considers employee career progress, employee-retention, and success of a company (Tharushika PATHIRANAGE, 2023). According to (Sharma, 2023) Employees has lower work-family conflict has more job satisfaction this will happened with the help of family-friendly policies, and supervisor support. Palumbu Rocco says ‘Accountants showed negative effects when dealing with work-life interplay’. They are attached and satisfy in their working culture where less struggle occurs between personal and professional life (Palumbo, 2023).

➤ *Digitalization*

Now-a-days world become digitalized, we are adopting a digital world. A study it shows the impact of technology and digitalization helps in the area of employee working activity, health, and work-life balance of employees (Maria Rosaria Gualano, 2023). Technology has a great impact in our society.

➤ *Conflicts*

This factor is very important to control in life then only a man will successfully face any kind of issues/problems. The work demands increase, change in technology, workers bring work at home. So, an improper development of balancing leads to a wide variety of negative outcomes from both personal and working life which may occure absenteeism, satisfaction at work may reduce, loyalty reduces, more turnover, and distress mentally increasing that affecting productivity. (Misun Lim, 2020) According to (Neha Agrawal, 2023) “The work-life balance and conflict overlap each other”.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study has reviewed various articles which are essential to the knowledge of working and personal life and equalize them. Reviewing various articles helps to get different views of authors towards the study.

To equalize working and personal life it enable employees at the workplace and for friendly working practices it needs flexible time, term time work, four and half day weeks, work sharing, and 9 days fortnight (Fleetwood & Steve, 2007).)These benefits will get with proper managing of work-life. Work-life balance facilitates successfully an organization by adopting a synergy culture, self-awareness, togetherness, etc. these all enhance level of psychological empowerment and also improve loyalty, honour, honesty, etc.,(Panda & Sahoo, 2021)

According to (P.Delecta, 2011) “To manage and allocate the time as per every aspect of life and he/she has to achieve work-life balance should not integrate problems”. Jones et al identified in their research understanding the best ways to manage employees who have the responsibility of childcare and eldercare and gender differences focused on the relationship between professional and family role rather than work and non-working community-related role (Jones.et.al., 2013). In a heterogeneous work environment, a diverse cultural background has formed. The studies show cultural differences viewed in education, personal life, and expectations towards organizational support (Gewinner & Irina, 2020). In view of Thomas, there are six concepts of working and non-working life balance multi-roles, equalize of multi-roles, the satisfaction of multiple roles, fulfill of role quietness between multi-roles, etc. They believe that working life and personal life balance needs operationalized, via measure development which validates across the national and cross-national sample (Thomas Kalliath, 2008)

The resources that are being into focused on continuous basis of work related and personal life based environment such as:

- a)Temporary-Based Resource- This is used to manage Time to do all-in-one needs or remote work, multiple work together, and use IT systems so, these may optimize time.
- b) Financial-Based resource- For satisfy wants and needs money helps for availability and the constraints of financial resource is addressed by budgeting and downshifting.

c) Control- To increase employee control and choose ‘how’ and ‘when’ initiatively make essential results like self-directed working team, flexible, empowerment, etc. (Greenblatt.E., 2002)

After the covid-19 period, the work-family balance for women changed with, an increase in household chores, the, rediscovering personal life values, and closeness, etc.(Toyin Ajibade Adisa, 2021). Women from rural family firms are largely positive and align their needs work flexibility, and calmness, secure, and well-being life (Nulleshi & Kalonaityte, 2023). It makes them attached to work. A married working woman finds difficulty to balance study and personal life together, likewise, an IT worker may face more difficulty in the work-life cycle because of various work and personal life-related issues. (Lakshmi & Prasanth, 2018). In their study it shows to understand the human needs and employees are not feeling down in organizational expectations on after-hour connectivity. And also they mention the socio-economic circumstances of the developing countries of south Asia during Covid-19 pandemic a lot of company adopted diatance work; this may change working world but after Covid-19 most of the corporates adopts these changes and they call it “Work From Home”. (Alwis, Hernwall, & Adikaram, 2022).

In a study, four major themes have been discovered in work-life balance such as increase household work, conflict, family values etc(Ajibade Adisa, Opeoluwa Aiyenitaju, & et.al., 2021). Elderly people may play important role, older people often needs help and care because of poor health, living alone, etc. The work-life balance is lower in females, single, telecaller, working with high workloads, and higher for those who were old has many responsibilities (Muayad Azzam, 2023).

A. Framework of working and personal life balance

There are three factors such as individual, organizational and societal factors. This framework explains easily various factors by using diagram (Thilagavathy S, 2021)

Fig.-01 Factors of work and personal life balance (Thilagavathy S, 2021).

IV. METHODOLOGY

An extensive literature review has been done, this research has an in-depth study of various literature. In this research secondary data has been taken that's why it is called a review paper. In chart-01 it is easier to identify from 2000-2023 articles that have been taken for review purposes, recently work-life balance-related articles and books have been taken. Next, there are many sources from which data has been collected 47% of the research paper has been taken which may successfully complete this paper. As per this study, it is been identified mostly a work-life balance-related topic assumed by India, chat:03 mentioned very clearly 21% of the article are from India. In chart: 04 it has been shown mostly from google scholar data have been taken.

Chart: 3 Based on articles that have been done in various countries.

Chart 1. A number of articles taken from 2000-2023 have mention

Chart 4: Search engines used in research.

Chart: 2 Many sources are used in this research.

V. DRAWBACKS OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE

The working and personal life has various issues depends on person to person. There are drawbacks which mentioned in table 2 it has different author's point of view as per their studies. This study is based on impact of work-life balance towards organizational development .

Table:2 The Drawbacks of work and personal life balance (Views of various authors)

Sl. No.	Drawbacks of work and personal life balance (Views of various authors)	
	Name of Article	Drawbacks
01	"work-life balance: a review of the meaning of the balance construct"	conflict increase during covid-19 when women having work and family duties together (thomas kalliath, 2008)
02	"discourses of work-life balance: negotiating 'genderblind' terms in organizations"	younger women faces issues mostly those who have children (smithson & stokoe, 2005)
03	"the impact of e-mail on work-life balance"	the pda email technology was mentioned that negative effect arise on employees who does remote work (ansumalini panda, 2021)
04	"Sandwich generation women in search for meaningful work and life"	For many women's work-life balance is not easy reachable (mervi rajahonka & kaija villman, 2022)
05	"Help and care to older parents in the digital society"	There is a need to properly taking care of parents but due to work pressure or improper balancing towards work and personal life difficulties may occur.(dr. Heidi gautun, 2023)
06	"A Study On Work-life balance in working women"	The problems and trouble of women are multi-dimensional. (Lakshmi & Prasanth, 2018)

VI. LIMITATIONS

We acknowledge the possibility of missing some papers unknowingly, which is unfortunately not included in this review paper. We consider not a particular set of papers integrated into a review paper, research paper, case study, and book section. Next, only the English language has been chosen for reviewing purposes which is also a drawback.

VII. RECOMMENDATION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Every article which is used in this study has some valuable suggestions that are very important to focus on. It is very important to follow suggestions based on our perspective. This study is a review where collected data from various sources has been taken, from those data it is recommended that work-life balance should follow the 80/20 rule, 20% of hard work effort can be given 80% of free time to enjoying life. This basic principle should be applicable to everyone in their life. We sometimes get indulged so much in work we cannot enjoy or manage our life happily for this reason the 80/20 rule should apply. In this study further research is required because it is still underexplored.

VIII. CONCLUSION

As we see that working life and personal life balance is essential to manage in an organization. Based on various studies it is assumed that work-life balance has some benefits and drawbacks. This study is a review paper, multiple authors give their own opinion based on work-life. There are various factors from different articles are mentioned where it needs more focus. According to such studies, It is a coordinate everyone in personal life, and managing the balance is compulsory for both working and personal life. This study has assumed limitations and gives recommendations for work-life balance for future development.

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